

Job Satisfaction of Industrial Workers of Bangladesh: A Study on Meghna Textile Mills Limited

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ABSTRACT: Job satisfaction is important for better performance. This research paper shows the various factors affect job satisfaction. To find the actual facts 50 respondents are selected randomly from Meghna Textiles Mills Ltd., Tongi Industrial Area, Gazipur, Dhaka for collecting data. A structured interview schedule is used to collect data. Brayfield-Rothe scale was used for measuring job satisfaction. 10 variables like proper supervision, recognition for good work, payment, promotional opportunities, work environment, proper increment, participation in decision making, allowances and bonus are selected as independent variables and job satisfaction of the workers is selected as dependent variable. The result of the study shows that significantly higher number of workers are dissatisfied with their job than those who are satisfied with their job. The results indicate that age and experiences are negatively correlated with job satisfaction. The industrialists can be benefited by reducing job dissatisfaction which will lead to higher performance and better industrial relation in the country. Changes should be made to get better performance by the workers for the betterment of the current situation of industries in Bangladesh.]

KEY WORDS: Job satisfaction, performances, industrial workers.

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is the pleasurable and emotional state resulting from the perception of one's job as fulfilling his/her job values, providing these values are compatible with one's need (Locke 1976). Job satisfaction or dissatisfaction is a function of perceived relationship between what one expects and obtains from one's job and how much importance or value one attributes to it. The study was designed to examine the relationship between job satisfaction and performance of the industrial worker in Bangladesh.

Since the publication of Hoppock's monograph on job satisfaction research on the topic of job attitudes has increased rapidly. According to the estimation of Locke (1976) more than 4000 articles had been published on this topic till 1976. Over Locke's definition of job satisfaction, Verhaegen (1979) claimed, "It seems to be impossible to arrive at any better definition because of the very nature of the subjects. The idea that job satisfaction is a result of interaction between the person and the environment is not new. Rosen and Rosen (1955) view job satisfaction as a consequence of the discrepancy between percepts and value standards. For this reason the researcher has chosen the topic as "Job Satisfaction and Performances of Industrial Workers of Bangladesh: A Study on Meghna Textile Mills Limited research work from Tongi Industrial Area, Gazipur, Dhaka.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to measure job satisfaction and performance of the industry workers. For fulfilling the main objective some specific objectives are assigned as follows:

1. To measure overall job satisfaction of industrial workers of Bangladesh.
2. To see whether there is any correlation between job satisfaction and the age of workers.
3. To measure the relative importance different job facets for job satisfaction.

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- To measure the important causes of dissatisfaction among the workers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the study out of 1100 workers in weaving section 50 workers are selected as respondents randomly. 50 percent (25) of sample workers are males and 50 percent (25) are females. Their ages were from 22 to 48 years (mean age being 39.68 years). Their education range was from class 2 to SSC pass. The study is conducted on the basis of primary and secondary data. Primary data are collected from the sample respondents and secondary data are collected from official records of Meghna Jute Mills Ltd., Tongi, its website and different publications. An interview schedule is used for collecting data. 10 variables like wages, recognition for good work, working environment, participation in decision making, proper supervision, promotional opportunities, opportunity for exchange of information, good relation with co-workers, job security and job status are selected as independent variables and job satisfaction of the workers is selected as dependent variable.

Collected data are processed in logical order. For measuring job satisfaction, the Brayfield-Rothe scale (Brayfield-Rothe 1951) is used. It measures overall job satisfaction rather than specific aspects of the job situation. It should yield a reliable and valid index. This scale is used for assessing global effective orientation to the job as a whole. Timing and Shifts are shown in the table 1.

Table 1. Timing and Shifts of the Mills.

Shifts	Group A	Group B
Shift- 1	6 am -10 am	10 am – 2 pm
Shift- 2	2 pm – 6 pm	6 pm – 10 pm
Shift- 3	10 pm – 6 pm	

Source: Official record of the Mills.

Range and mean of demographic variables of the respondents are as follows :

Table 2. Range and Mean of Demographic Variables.

Subject	Age	Education	Experience	Performance	Income
Range	22-48	grade2-5	2-25	1301-2320	3200-6000
Mean	34.68	grade5	9.34	1748	2820

Source: Prepared on the basis of field survey.

ANALYSES AND FINDINGS

Mean ranks : The mean ranks and ranks orders of the workers ratings of relative importance of the 10 specific aspects of the job to their overall job satisfaction are given below in the table 3.

Table 3. Men Ranks and Rank Orders of the Workers Ratings of Specific Job Facets in Terms of Their Importance of Job Satisfaction

Variables	Mean Ranks	Rank Orders
Wages	4.50	1
Recognition for good work	3.58	2
Work environment	3.54	3
Participation in decision making	3.48	4
Proper supervision	3.48	5
Proper increment	3.48	6
Promotional opportunities	3.20	7
Timely payment	2.86	8
Allowances	2.66	9
Bonus	2.18	10

Source: Measured on the basis of field survey.

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The results in the table shows that wage has been considered by the workers as the most important facet for job satisfaction (rank-1). On the other hand job status has been rated as the least important facet of job satisfaction (rank 10). The other 10 facets have been assigned ranks in between these two positions.

Job Satisfaction Scores: Job satisfaction scores are presented in the table 4.

Table 4. Distribution of Job Satisfaction Scores of the Workers

Job satisfaction scores	Frequency
40 - 45	6
45 - 50	17
50 - 55	15
55 - 60	12

Source: Measured on the basis of field survey.

Job satisfaction scores of the workers were grouped into classes intervals and the corresponding frequencies were arranged in tabular forms out of 50 workers, 12 workers have job satisfaction above 54 i.e. 55 to 60. Then 24% are satisfied workers and 76% of them are considered dissatisfied.

Causes of Job Dissatisfaction: Causes of dissatisfaction and their ranks are presented in the table 5.

Table 5. The Important Cause of Job Dissatisfaction as Perceived by the Workers.

Perceived Causes of Job Dissatisfaction	Percentage of the Workers
Poor wage	26%
Improper supervision	16%
Non-recognition for good works	10%
Lag in payment	9%
Lack of promotional opportunity	9%
Bad work environment	8%
Improper increment	8%
Lack of participation in decision making	7%
Lack of allowances	4%
Improper bonus	3%

Source: Measured on the basis of field survey.

The result in the above table shows the workers' 10 different factors as causes of job dissatisfaction. However, the highest number of respondents (26%) have considered poor wage as the most important cause of dissatisfaction followed by improper supervision, non-recognition for good work, lag in payment, lack of promotional opportunities, bad work environment, improper increment, lack of participation in decision making, lack of allowances and lack of bonus.

The result of the study shows that 76% of the workers are dissatisfied with their job and 24% are satisfied with it. The difference is highly significant. The workers do not get their compensation in proper time. Lack of proper fringe benefit, promotional opportunity in sufficient income, recognition for good work etc. also are the causes of job satisfaction. It also may be the government policies to enhance their job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The important causes of job dissatisfaction as perceived by the workers show that higher number of workers said poor wage is the most important cause of job dissatisfaction. Because now-a-days cost of living is higher than that of the workers' wages. They are unable to maintain their family with their wages. Our study showed that a quite number of factors have been considered by the subjects as both job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. So, it appears from the results that the satisfaction variables are not unidirectional.

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Finally we can conclude that on industrial organization benefit immensely by adopting appropriate measures in the light of the present findings to reduce job dissatisfaction and enhance job satisfaction of its employees which are extremely important for promoting industrial relations, productivity and productivity of the industry.

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